

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 04

Version 1.0 from 2018/03/26

openEO core API prototype including Proof of Concept

Change history

Issue	Date	Author(s)	Description
0.1	2018/03/09	Edzer Pebesma, Matthias Mohr, WWU	First draft
0.2	2018/03/20	Jeroen Dries, VITO	Internal review
1.0	2018/03/26	Matthias Schramm, TU Wien	Final review and creation of final version

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Table of Contents

- 1 Executive summary** **6**

- 2 Links to the demonstrator** **6**
 - 2.1 Link to the API specification, documentation, and proof-of-concept 6
 - 2.2 Selected use-cases 6
 - 2.3 Links to blog post and videos 7
 - 2.4 Videos demonstrating client-back-end interactions 7

- 3 Succeeded use case/client/back-end combination** **7**

- 4 Discussion** **8**

- 5 References** **8**

List of Tables

3.1 Combinations of clients, back-ends and use cases that were successfully tested
(numbers refer to use case 1-3) 8

List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

EO Earth Observation

NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

1 Executive summary

The openEO EU project [1] develops an open API to connect R, python and JavaScript clients to big Earth observation cloud back-ends in a simple and unified way. This deliverable (of type “demonstrator”) demonstrates the existence of this API and its functioning for a selected number of use cases, by pointing to the API documentation and to functioning software implementation where an R, Python and JavaScript client connect to a variety of back-ends. The purpose of the proof-of-concept is to inform the Earth Observation community about the progress made in openEO by ways of the proof of concept, and this document contains the links to the on-line, public documentation created (API, descriptions, blog post with demonstration videos); it does not copy those.

The API description, the description of the use cases, the client and back-end drivers developed and the demonstrations showing that they actually work well together all indicate that the openEO API is a feasible concept.

2 Links to the demonstrator

2.1 Link to the API specification, documentation, and proof-of-concept

The core concepts and API specification for openEO are found at <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-api/index.html>.

The proof-of-concept is described at: <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-api/poc/index.html>.

2.2 Selected use-cases

To demonstrate the feasibility of the openEO concept, a prototype has been developed that focuses on using clients for analysing Earth Observation imagery in cloud-based back-ends. Features like user authentication or accounting have, on purpose, not been addressed in this proof of concept.

During the openEO kick-off meeting in Oct 2017, three use cases were selected to demonstrate the openEO proof-of-concept. They include

1. Deriving minimum NDVI measurements over pixel time series of Sentinel 2 imagery
2. Creating a monthly aggregated Sentinel 1 product from a custom Python script
3. Computing time series of zonal (regional) statistics of Sentinel 2 imagery over user-uploaded polygons

All case studies follow the pattern:

- Check whether data is available at the back-end
- Check that needed processes are available
- Create a job at the back-end
- Define output

- Retrieve output
- Stop the job (and the service)

In the documentation, found at <https://open-eo.github.io/openeo-api/poc/index.html>, the example API calls with (example) requests and responses are given.

2.3 Links to blog post and videos

The following blog post on the <http://openeo.org/> project home page describes the proof of concept use cases to a wide audience:

<http://openeo.org/openeo/news/2018/03/17/poc.html>

2.4 Videos demonstrating client-back-end interactions

The following videos were created to demonstrate successful client-server interactions (also linked from the blog post):

1. GRASS GIS (mundialis) accessed with curl (UC 1,2,3): [view](#)¹
2. WCPS (EURAC) accessed with R client (UC1): [view](#)²
3. R back-end (WWU) accessed with R client (UC1): [view](#)³
4. R back-end (WWU) accessed with R client (UC3): [view](#)⁴
5. Sentinel-Hub (Sinergise), OpenShift (EODC) and WCPS (EURAC) accessed with the Web Editor, based on the JavaScript client (UC1): [view](#)⁵
6. R back-end (WWU) accessed with the Web Editor, based on the JavaScript client (UC3): [view](#)⁶
7. GeoPySpark (VITO) accessed with the Python client (UC1): [view](#)⁷

3 Succeeded use case/client/back-end combination

The combinations of clients, back-ends and use cases that were successfully executed are listed in table 3.1

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NgF1WgCtSiM>

²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NoD0nVGM3ww>

³https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yb_QfIO-uIE

⁴https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LYnad6KC_CU

⁵<https://youtu.be/zDaQkw0NhpY>

⁶<https://youtu.be/XsPbKypUuIE>

⁷<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qtIp9OC0qHY>

back-end	Python client	R client	JavaScript client
GRASS GIS, mundialis		1,2,3	
OpenShift, EODC		1	1
GeoPySpark, VITO	1,2,3		
Sentinel Hub, Sinergise			1
WCPS, EURAC	1	1	1
R back-end, WWU		1,2,3	1,3

Table 3.1: Combinations of clients, back-ends and use cases that were successfully tested (numbers refer to use case 1-3)

4 Discussion

The API description, the description of the use cases, the client and back-end drivers developed and the demonstrations showing that they actually work well together all indicate that the openEO API is a feasible concept. The amount of working dedicated openEO clients (3) and back-ends (6) exceeds by far the tentative goals that were set in the project proposal for this early stage of the project.

By intention, the use-cases were picked ambitiously: they address variation of multiple attributes (bands) over space and time, user-defined functions in R and Python that need to be evaluated on the back-end, and integration of imagery over polygons, and delivering results in various forms (file formats, web services). It was clear from the start that not all back-ends would be able (or will ever be able) to cope with all of them. This has led to good discussions about the differences between back-ends, and has anticipated upcoming decisions on what can become compulsory and what will have to become optional parts of the openEO API.

5 References

- [1] E. Pebesma, W. Wagner, M. Schramm, A. Von Beringe, C. Paulik, M. Neteler, J. Reiche, J. Verbesselt, J. Dries, E. Goor, and et al., “openEO – a common, open source interface between earth observation data infrastructures and front-end applications,” *Zenodo*, Nov 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/1065474>

